

Table S1. List of studies included in our literature review (n = 32). If a publication provided findings from separate data collection in multiple states or findings from the same state across several years of separate data collection, we included the data from this publication as multiple data entries when compiling our data (data entries = 44). The ‘Year(s)’ column of the table refers to the years of data collection for the specified study.

Data Entry Number	State Abbreviation	Year(s)	References (Numbered)
1	OH	1985	1. Swanson, D. A. Jr., R. J. Stoll, and W. L. Culbertson. 2005. Attitudes, preferences, and characteristics, of Ohio’s Spring Turkey hunters, 1985–2001. Pages 325–330 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 9 th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA.
2	MI	1985*	2. Hazel, K. L., E. E. Jr. Langenau, and R. L. Levine. 1990. Dimensions of hunting satisfaction: multiple-satisfactions of wild turkey hunting. <i>Leisure Sciences</i> 12:383–393.
3	WV	1988-1993	3. Taylor, C. I., J. C. Pack, W. K. Igo, J. E. Evans, P. R. Johansen, and G. H. Sharp. 1996. West Virginia spring turkey hunters and hunting. Pages 259–268 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 7 th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Rapid City, South Dakota, USA.
4	AR	1988	4. Cartwright, M. E., and R. A. Smith. 1990. Attitudes, opinions, and characteristics of a select group of Arkansas spring turkey hunters. Pages 177–187 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 6 th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Charleston, South Carolina, USA.
5	MO	1988	5. Vangilder, L. D., S. L. Sheriff, and G. S. Olson. 1990. Characteristics, attitudes, and preferences of Missouri's spring turkey hunters. Pages 167–176 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 6th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Charleston, South Carolina, USA.
6	FL	1988	6. Eichholz, N. F., and S. B. Hardin. 1990. Turkey hunter satisfaction in Florida. Pages 319–327 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 1990 Annual Conference of the Southeastern Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. Richmond, Virginia, USA.
7	MO	1988	7. Baumann, D. P. Jr., L. D. Vangilder, C. I. Taylor, R. Engel-Wilson, R. O. Kimmel, and G.A. Wunz. (1990). Expenditures for wild turkey hunting. Pages

			157–166 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 6 th National Turkey Symposium. Charleston, South Carolina, USA.
8	AZ	1989	7. –
9	MN	1989	7. –
10	PA	1989	7. –
11	SC	1989	7. –
12	WV	1989	7. –
13	OH	1989	1. Swanson, D. A. Jr., R. J. Stoll, and W. L. Culbertson. 2005. Attitudes, preferences, and characteristics, of Ohio's Spring Turkey hunters, 1985–2001. Pages 325–330 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 9 th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA.
14	VA	1990	8. Bittner, L. A., and H. P. Hite. 1991. Attitudes and opinions of Virginia's spring turkey hunters towards safety issues. Pages 124–132 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 1991 Annual Conference Southeastern Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. White Sulphur Springs, West Virginia, USA.
15	GA	1991-1993	9. Thackston, R. E., and H. T. Holbrook. 1996. Responsive management survey of turkey hunting on Georgia wildlife management areas. Pages 253–257 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 7 th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Rapid City, South Dakota, USA
16	MS	1993	10. Godwin, K. D., R. S. Seiss, C. C. Shropshire, D. A. Miller, G. A. Hurs, and B.D. Leopold. 1997. Characteristics and attitudes of wild turkey hunters in Mississippi. Pages 426–437 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 1997 Annual Conference of the Southeastern Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. Oklahoma City, Oklahoma, USA.
17	MS	1994	11. Forbes, J. T., K. D. Goldwin, and G.A. Hurst. 1996. Attitudes of wild turkey hunters toward potential regulation changes in Mississippi. Pages 457–465 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 1996 Annual Conference of the Southeastern Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. Hot Springs, Arkansas, USA.
18	MO	1994	12. Isabelle, J. L., and R.A. Reitz. 2016. Characteristics, attitudes, and preferences of spring wild turkey hunters in Missouri. Pages 249–258 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 11 th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Tucson, Arizona, USA.
19	MO	1994	13. Caslena, M. J., C. S. Rosenberry, and R. C. Boyd. 2010. Knowledge, characteristics, and attitudes of wild turkey hunters in Pennsylvania. Pages 41–48

			<i>in Proceedings of the 10th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Shepherdstown, West Virginia, USA.</i>
20	OH	1996	1. Swanson, D. A. Jr., R. J. Stoll, and W. L. Culbertson. 2005. Attitudes, preferences, and characteristics, of Ohio's Spring Turkey hunters, 1985–2001. Pages 325–330 <i>in Proceedings of the 9th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA.</i>
21	TX	1997	14. Harmel-Garza, D., C. E. Adams, J. K. Thomas, and M. J. Peterson. 1999. Characteristics of wild turkey hunters in Texas. Pages 390–401 <i>in Proceedings of the 1999 Annual Conference of the Southeastern Association of Fish and Wildlife Agencies. Greensboro, North Carolina, USA.</i>
22	VA	1998	15. Wynveen, C. J., D. A. Cavin, B. A. Wright, and W. E. Hammitt. 2005. Determinants of a quality wild turkey hunting season. <i>Environmental Management</i> 36:117–124.
23	KS	1998-1999	16. Van Why, K. R., R. D. Applegate, T. T. Cable, and P. S. Gipson. 2001. Survey of Kansas wild turkey hunters: experiences, opinions, and satisfactions. Kansas State University Agriculture Experiment Station and Cooperative Extension Service, Manhattan, Kansas, USA.
24	MO	2000	12. Isabelle, J. L., and R.A. Reitz. 2016. Characteristics, attitudes, and preferences of spring wild turkey hunters in Missouri. Pages 249–258 <i>in Proceedings of the 11th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Tucson, Arizona, USA.</i>
25	SD	2000	17. Gigliotti, L. M. 2000. South Dakota Spring Turkey Hunter Opinion Survey Report – 2000. Report ID#: HD-21-00. SAM. South Dakota Game, Fish, and Parks. Pierre, South Dakota, USA.
26	PA	2001	13. Caslena, M. J., C. S. Rosenberry, and R. C. Boyd. 2010. Knowledge, characteristics, and attitudes of wild turkey hunters in Pennsylvania. Pages 41–48 <i>in Proceedings of the 10th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Shepherdstown, West Virginia, USA.</i>
27	OH	2001	1. Swanson, D. A. Jr., R. J. Stoll, and W. L. Culbertson. 2005. Attitudes, preferences, and characteristics, of Ohio's Spring Turkey hunters, 1985–2001. Pages 325–330 <i>in Proceedings of the 9th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Grand Rapids, Michigan, USA.</i>
28	MS	2003-2004	18. Hunt, K. M., J. T. Arnold, and V. Mittapalli. 2004. Characteristics of wild turkey hunters in Mississippi & their attitudes towards wild turkey management

			issues. Human Dimensions & Conservation Law Enforcement Laboratory Forest & Wildlife Research Center Mississippi State University, Starkville, Mississippi, USA.
29	MD	2007	19. Maryland Department of Natural Resources [MDNR]. 2007. Maryland spring turkey hunter survey – results summary August 2007. Maryland Department of Natural Resources, Annapolis, Maryland, USA.
30	PA	2008	13. Caslena, M. J., C. S. Rosenberry, and R. C. Boyd. 2010. Knowledge, characteristics, and attitudes of wild turkey hunters in Pennsylvania. Pages 41–48 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 10th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Shepherdstown, West Virginia, USA.
31	SD	2009	20. Gigliotti, L. M. 2009. South Dakota Spring Turkey Hunter Opinion Survey Report – 2009. Report ID#: HD-4-09. AMS. South Dakota Game, Fish, and Parks. Pierre, South Dakota, USA.
32	MO	2011	12. Isabelle, J. L., and R.A. Reitz. 2016. Characteristics, attitudes, and preferences of spring wild turkey hunters in Missouri. Pages 249–258 <i>in</i> Proceedings of the 11th National Wild Turkey Symposium. Tucson, Arizona, USA.
33	NY	2013	21. Siemer, W. F., J. R. Boulanger, D. J. Decker, and M. S. Baumer. 2014. Activities and satisfactions of fall turkey hunters in New York State. Human Dimensions Research Unit Publication Series 14–1. Department of Natural Resources, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York, USA.
34	NY	2013	22. Boulanger, J.R., W. F. Siemer, D. J. Decker, and M. S. Baumer. 2013. Turkey hunting in New York: Hunter activities and views on regulations. Human Dimensions Research Unit Series Publication 13-7. Department of Natural Resources, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York, USA.
35	MN	2014	23. Schroeder, S. A. 2015. Minnesota Spring Wild Turkey Hunting: A Study of Hunters’ Opinions and Activities. University of Minnesota, Minnesota Cooperative Fish and Wildlife Research Unit, Department of Fisheries, Wildlife, and Conservation Biology, St. Paul, Minnesota, USA.
36	FL	2015	24. Leal, A., J. N. Rumble, and S. Anderson. 2016. Turkey Hunters’ Opinions and Attitudes: Florida. PIE2015/16-3a. University of Florida/IFAS Center for Public Issues Education, Gainesville, Florida, USA.

37	TN	2015	25. Maldonado, C. E. 2017. Motivation and Support for Regulatory Changes: A Typology of Tennessee Wild Turkey Hunters. Thesis, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, Tennessee, USA.
38	MS	2015-2018	26. Butler, A. B., and G. Wang, G. 2022. Connecting hunt outcomes to the demographics, behaviors, and experiences of wild turkey hunters in Mississippi. <i>Wildlife Society Bulletin</i> 46:e1268.
39	MD	2017	27. Maryland Department of Natural Resources [MDNR]. 2017. Maryland spring turkey hunter survey – results summary August 2017. Maryland Department of Natural Resources, Annapolis, Maryland, USA.
40	SD	2018	28. Longmire, C. L. 2018. Spring Turkey Hunter Opinion Survey – 2018. South Dakota Game, Fish, and Parks, Pierre, South Dakota, USA.
41	SC	2018	29. South Carolina Department of Natural Resources [SCDNR]. 2018. 2018 avid South Carolina turkey hunter survey. South Carolina Department of Natural Resources, Columbia, South Carolina, USA.
42	SC	2020	30. Downs, L. K. 2021. Human dimensions of recreational hunting and angling in South Carolina. Thesis, Clemson University, Clemson, South Carolina, USA.
43	ID	2020	31. Idaho Department of Fish and Game [IDFG]. 2022. Idaho wild turkey hunter opinion survey. Idaho Department of Fish and Game, Boise, Idaho, USA.
44	VA	2023	32. Valdez, R. X. and M. G. White. 2024. Results of the 2023 Virginia turkey hunter survey. Virginia Department of Wildlife Resources. Henrico, Virginia, USA.

*Date is inferred from publication as exact date is not listed and author did not respond to attempts to contact.

Figure S1. Comparison of trends in estimated number of wild turkey hunters to assess wild turkey hunting participation from 2000-2025 (where data is available). Trendline is featured for each state via a gray, dashed line. Data is compiled from state agency estimates. Importantly, only states using estimates of wild turkey hunter numbers via surveys were included – we did not use any license/permit sale data because this is not a true estimate of hunter participation. Pennsylvania is isolated from the other states and has a unique y-axis because of the large discrepancy in number of hunters in this state compared to the others included – every other plot for each individual state uses the same y-axis. Please see sources listed in Table S2.

Table S2. Sources used to generate the estimated number of wild turkey hunters plot displayed in Figure S1.

State	Years	Source(s)
Alabama	2020-2024	<p>Duda, M. D., M. Jones, T. Beppler, A. Center, A. Criscione, P. Doherty, G. L. Hughes, J. Morris, and A. Lanier. 2024. Alabama hunter harvest 2023-2024. Responsive Management National Office, Harrisonburg, Virginia, USA.</p> <p>Duda, M. D., M. Jones, T. Beppler, S. J. Bissell, A. Center, A. Criscione, P. Doherty, G. L. Hughes, C. Gerken, and A. Lanier. 2020. Alabama hunter harvest 2019-2020. Responsive Management National Office, Harrisonburg, Virginia, USA.</p> <p>Bryant, S. 2018. Alabama hunting survey 2016-2017. Grant Number W-35, Study 6. Alabama Division of Wildlife and Freshwater Fisheries: Wildlife Restoration Program, Montgomery, AL, USA.</p>
Georgia	2020-2022	<p>Georgia Department of Natural Resources – Wildlife Resources Division [GDNR – WRD]. 2024. Wild turkey program FY2024 harvest monitoring. Georgia Department of Natural Resources – Wildlife Resources Division, Social Circle, GA, USA.</p>
Louisiana	2005-2024	<p>Cedotal, C. 2024. LDWF wild turkey program overview/annual report 2024. Louisiana Department of Wildlife and Fisheries, Baton Rouge, LA, USA.</p>

Indiana	2000-2020	Backs, S. E. 2020. Spring wild turkey harvest results – 2020. Publication No. 2064. Indiana Department of Natural Resources – Division of Fish and Wildlife, Indianapolis, IN, USA.
Kansas	2000-2013	Pitman, J. Turkey harvest report: spring 2013. Kansas Department of Wildlife and Parks, Pratt, KS, USA.
Nebraska	2014-2024	Provided by C. Gizel (Wild Turkey Program Manager, Nebraska Game & Parks Commission & National Wild Turkey Federation)
North Carolina	2011-2024	North Carolina Wildlife Resources Commission – Wildlife Management Division [NCWRC-WDW]. 2024. Harvest statistics. < https://www.ncwildlife.gov/hunting/harvest-statistics#StateHunterHarvestSurveyEstimates-1441 > Accessed July 2025. Missing reports provided by H. Plumpton (Upland Game Bird Biologist, North Carolina Wildlife Resource Commission – Wildlife Management Division
Oklahoma	2000-2024	York, B. 2025. Final performance report. Oklahoma Department of Wildlife Conservation, Oklahoma City, OK, USA.
Pennsylvania	2005-2024	Pennsylvania Game Commission – Bureau of Wildlife Management [PGC-BWM]. 2024. Estimated number of hunters by species. Pennsylvania Game Commission – Bureau of Wildlife Management, Harrisburg, PA, USA.
South Carolina	2007-2024	South Carolina Department of Natural Resources [SCDNR]. 2024. Wildlife – wild turkeys: archived reports and publications.

		< https://www.dnr.sc.gov/wildlife/turkey/archive.html > Accessed July 2025.
Texas	2000-2018	Purvis, J. 2018. Small game harvest survey results 1998-99 thru 2017-18. Texas Parks and Wildlife, Austin, TX, USA.